

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MWAMBENE****FIRST NAME: JAMES****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The best way to present an academic essay is to structure it into three main parts. These main parts include:**
 - Introduction, body, and conclusion¹**
 - Objectives, introduction, and conclusion
 - Purpose, body, and conclusion
 - Aim, thesis, and methodology

2. **Plagiarism in academia is regarded as “wrong and unethical” because it is not fair to take someone’s work and not give him or her credit. Which statement best describes the word plagiarism?**
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the author of that source of information
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information²**
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses his or her own words in the document
 - Plagiarism occurs only when one is copying information from the internet

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

² EUCLID, 5.

3. **Planning to write a research paper starts with the identification of a topic or an aim of research which is based on a research question. There are three types of research questions:**
- Knowledge, practical and findings
 - Background, analysis, and application
 - Conceptual, practical, and applied³**
 - Publication, practical, and discussion
4. **Once the paper is published, it is normally presented at international conferences. The research papers are presented in the form of oral presentations and posters. However, the oral presentation has an advantage over poster presentation because;**
- It gets immediate feedback during the question and answers time⁴**
 - It is self-explanatory
 - It requires more than two people to present it
 - It is always pasted on the wall

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 81.

5. **Although bibliography-style citation and author-date citation practices are the same in principles; but somehow they are different in their application. Which statement best describes the difference between the two citations?**
- In bibliography-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the beginning of the sentence in which you refer to it whilst in author-date citations; you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to it
 - In bibliography-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the middle of the sentence in which you refer to it whilst in author-date citations; you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to it
 - In bibliography-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it whilst in author-date citations; you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to it⁵**
 - In bibliography-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a lower case number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it whilst in author-date citations; you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to it

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 88.

6. **Incorrect use of spellings affects the quality and power of writing. The correct spellings depend on the type of English language one is using, either American or British. The most reliable data source for spellings is**
- Given's dictionary
 - Donald's dictionary
 - Milan's dictionary
 - Merriam Webster's dictionary⁶**
7. **Identifying and developing the right research topic makes the research original and show the character of having a desire to contribute to the existing knowledge base. To achieve this, the researcher needs to consider the following issues:**
- The potential audience, reference, and conclusion
 - The potential audience, consent and research rights
 - The potential audience, the intellectual value, and worth of the study, personal and professional goals, and ethical considerations⁷**
 - Potential audience and study discussion

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 163.

⁷ Bloomberg Linda Dale d Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 6.

8. **Sample selection is an important aspect of the dissertation because the researcher's credibility lies in the quality of procedures used to select the research participants. Purposive and random sampling methods are used for the selection of participants. However, they differ in their application:**
- The purposive sampling method is used in quantitative research while a random sampling procedure is used in qualitative research⁸**
 - The purposive sampling method is used in qualitative research while a random sampling procedure is used in applied research
 - The purposive sampling method is used in practical research while a random sampling procedure is used in desk-based research.
 - The purposive sampling method is used in descriptive research while random sampling is used in analytical research
9. **Translating the names of some Member States of the World Health Organization from their original names to the English language is not allowed. Also, the names of the Member countries are written in full. Which Member country is correctly written?**
- the United Republic of Tanzania⁹**
 - Côte d'Ivoire
 - Libya
 - North Korea

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 68.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 14-15.

10. **The WHO publication format for presenting items in a reference list is based on the Vancouver style, formulated by the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors, but with certain adaptations to meet the WHO's particular needs. For reference list, it is recommended:**

- To list all authors when there are three or fewer and when there are four or more, give only the first author's name and add "et al."
- The name of the journal must be written in full and title of the book or journal *Italicized*
- With Harvard style, the date is placed in parentheses immediately after the authors' names, followed by a full stop
- All of them above¹⁰**

¹⁰ World Health Organization, 25-26.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.